

Studies on *Bis N*-Phenylhydroxamic Acids as Metal Complexing Ligands. Part VI. Determination of Formation Constants of Al (III) Chelates

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Manuscript received 25 February 1974 ; revised 1st October 1974 ; accepted 1 October 1974

The formation of aluminium complexes [Al₂R(RH)₂(OH)₂] of succinyl-, glutaryl-, adipyl-, and pimelyl-*bis-N*-phenylhydroxamic acids (R_sH₂, R_gH₂, R_aH₂, R_pH₂ respectively) have been studied potentiometrically in 1 : 2 aqueous ethanol at constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.25$). The step-stability constants of Al (III) chelates are, in general, in the ligand order R_pH₂ > R_aH₂ > R_gH₂ > R_sH₂.

THE aluminium complexes of succinyl-, glutaryl-, adipyl-, and pimelyl-*bis-N*-phenylhydroxamic acids (R_sH₂, R_gH₂, R_aH₂ and R_pH₂ respectively) have been reported earlier¹. The complex compounds of the type [Al₂R(RH)₂(OH)₂] have been described. The formation constants of such aluminium complexes with these ligands have been determined in 1:2 aqueous ethanol in presence of requisite amount of sodium perchlorate to maintain constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.25$).

Let us consider a number of different solutions containing aluminium perchlorate, RH₂ (ligand) and free perchloric acid of known strengths and let them be titrated with a standard NaOH solution. In the formation of [Al₂R(RH)₂(OH)₂] complexes, the reaction between the ligand and the aluminium ion may be assumed to take place in a stepwise manner, as stated below :

The hydrolysis of Al₂R(RH)₂²⁺ ions begins in a stepwise manner on titration with alkali.

Using the following relations which hold good after the attainment of equilibrium at any stage of titration and for electroneutrality of the solution,

$$M = 2M_3 + 2M_4 + 2M_5 \quad \dots (4)$$

$$R = R_2 + R_1 + R_0 + 3M_3 + 3M_4 + 3M_5 \quad \dots (5)$$

$$2M_3 + M_4 + P + \text{H}^+ = 3M + F + \text{OH}^- + R_1 + 2R_0 \quad \dots (6)$$

where M, R, P and F are initial concentrations of Al(ClO₄)₃, ligand, alkali and free acid respectively and M₃, M₄, M₅, R₀, R₁, R₂, H⁺ and OH⁻ are equilibrium concentrations of Al₂R(RH)₂²⁺, Al₂R(RH)₂(OH)⁺, Al₂R(RH)₂(OH)₂, R²⁻, RH⁻, RH₂, acid and alkali respectively, one may deduce.

$\bar{n}_{\text{OH}}$ = the average number of (OH) groups attached to the ion Al₂R(RH)₂²⁺

$$= \frac{M_4 + 2M_5}{M_3 + M_4 + M_5} = \frac{2M_4 + 4M_5}{M}$$

$$= \left[\frac{2(P - F + \text{H}^+ - \text{OH}^-)}{M} - 4 \right] - \frac{2R_1 \left(1 + \frac{2k_1^*}{[\text{H}^+]} \right)}{M} \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\text{and } R_1 = (R - 3M/2) / \left(\frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2^*} + 1 + \frac{k_1^*}{[\text{H}^+]} \right) \quad \dots (8)$$

where k₂^{*} and k₁^{*} are step acid dissociation constants of ligand RH₂: the step dissociations are represented as RH₂ ⇌ RH⁻ + H⁺; RH⁻ ⇌ R²⁻ + H⁺ and the determination of which has been reported in an earlier communication².

On plotting $\bar{n}_{\text{OH}}$ against pH, one may find out the values of pK₄ and pK₅ by projection-strip method³, where K₄ = M₄ × [H⁺]/M₃ and K₅ = M₅ × [H⁺]/M₄.

The step acid dissociation of Al₂R(RH)₂²⁺ ions may also be stated as

and the step-stability constants, k₄ = $\frac{[\text{RAIRAI}^+(\text{RH})]}{[\text{R}^-\text{Al}^+\text{RAI}^+(\text{RH})]}$

and k₅ = $\frac{[\text{RAIRAIR}]}{[\text{RAIRAI}^+\text{R}^-]}$ may be calculated from the relations.

$$\log k_4 = \text{pk}^* - \text{pK}_4; \text{ and } \log k_5 = \text{pk}^* - \text{pK}_5; \dots (9)$$

where $\text{pk}^* = \frac{1}{2}(\text{pk}_2^* + \text{pk}_1^*)$. Therefore the compounds Al₂R(RH)₂(OH)₂ may also be stated by Al₂R₃, 2H₂O.

Experimental

All chemicals used were either of A.R. quality or properly purified. Measurements were performed in 1:2 aqueous ethanol by titrating potentiometrically a 100 ml solution containing known amounts of aluminium ion, ligand, and free perchloric acid with a standard NaOH solution at a temperature of 33° ± 0.5. Ionic strength of the medium ($\mu=0.25$) was maintained constant by adding requisite amount of sodium perchlorate. The results are based on

duplicate titrations made under identical conditions and with three different aluminium ion concentrations, which were of $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ to $2 \times 10^{-3}M$.

In order to determine the final acid concentration a graphical method was employed⁴. For this purpose pH values of a number of $HClO_4$ solutions of known strength in 1:2 aqueous ethanol and having the same ionic strength were plotted against negative logarithm of acid concentrations.

The step-acid dissociation constants of the ligands were determined in a similar way under identical conditions and are also shown in Table 1. The $\bar{n}_{OH}$ and R_1 values were calculated using equations (7) and (8). The evaluation of pK_4 and pK_5 were made from formation curves (Fig. 1) by projection-

Fig. 1.

strip method. The values of $\log k_4$ and $\log k_5$ were calculated from the relation (9). The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEP-ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS AND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF AL(III) CHELATES

Ligand	pk_2^*	pk_1^*	pk^*	By projection		$\log k_4$	$\log k_5$
				strip-method	pk_5		
$R_s H_2$	9.37	10.37	9.87	5.40	5.52	4.47	4.33
$R_g H_2$	9.36	10.46	9.91	4.71	4.91	5.20	5.00
$R_a H_2$	9.91	10.01	9.96	4.56	4.74	5.40	5.22
$R_p H_2$	9.87	10.22	10.04	4.39	4.63	5.65	5.41

Discussion

An inspection of the dissociation constants (pk^*) of the ligands reveals that at the interpolation of CH_2 groups between the two hydroxamic acid residues the acidic groups are made weaker. The step stability constants $-k_4$ and k_5 of Al(III) chelates, are, in general, in the ligand order $R_p H_2 >$

$R_a H_2 > R_g H_2 > R_s H_2$. As has been expected⁵ the increase of chain length leads to increased stability. The stabilities of these chelates are observed to be related directly with the average pk^* values of the ligands. The more basic are the ligands the more stable are their chelates. These trends have also been observed in many others cases^{6,7}.

As the CH_2 groups are electron repelling, with the increase of chain length the lone pair of electrons on the carbonyl oxygen are more available for $M \leftarrow O$ bond formation. Therefore, the complex with $R_p H_2$ should be the most stable. Actually it has been observed. The chelation between Al^{3+} and $R_p H_2$ giving the product $Al_2(R_p)_3$, may be represented as in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2

But stability constants of $R_a H_2$ and $R_p H_2$ are very close; so it may be suggested that there is a limit of chain length beyond which this effect is not appreciable.

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